

BATTERY2LIFE

Press Release

Giving a second life to electric vehicles' batteries!

As the electric vehicle (EV) revolution is here, with the multiple benefits the electric vehicles provide, there is an impending issue on what needs to be done with the EVs batteries which have reached the end of their "automotive" life but still have a residual capacity of about 70-80%. This residual capacity can be still exploitable for other non-EV storage applications aiming to facilitate the green energy transition and promote the Renewable Energy Source (RES) share in all electricity grids. BATTERY2LIFE has everything covered!

BATTERY2LIFE is a Horizon Europe project that will facilitate the smooth transition of batteries to 2nd life use and boost the innovation of the European Battery Industry by providing enablers to implement open, adaptable smart Battery Management Systems (BMSes) and improved system designs towards reliable reconfiguration of used batteries. *"The number of electric vehicle (EV) batteries no longer appropriate for automotive use will dramatically increase in the next years and it is crucial to find solutions on how to reuse them in the interest of environment, society and economy"*, mentions Dr Angelos Amditis, the BATTERY2LIFE project coordinator and Research & Development Director of the Institute of Communication and Computer Systems ([ICCS](#)).

The Battery2Life consortium will work on introducing two new battery system design frameworks serving the upcoming market needs: the first supports the business transition for the initial market by restructuring existing battery design patterns while the second one introduces completely new design principles for 1st and 2nd life of the battery. These new design frameworks will be deployed and evaluated for serving two promising and sustainable business cases: domestic storage application in Austria and a grid-scale storage application in Greece. The findings will be used to estimate the impact of the project results on the environment and the European economy and to prepare recommendations for standardisation Technical Committees.

BATTERY2LIFE project, which is comprised of 11 partners from different European countries, officially launched its activities with the organisation of the consortium kick-off meeting that was held in Athens, Greece on 23 & 24 January 2024!

For more information about the project please contact:

Dr Angelos Amditis, Research & Development Director of the Institute of Communication and Computer Systems (ICCS) and BATTERY2LIFE project coordinator.

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or CINEA. Neither the European Union nor CINEA can be held responsible for them.

Email: a.amditis@iccs.gr

Project Facts	
Duration	36 months (January 2024- December 2026)
Funding	Co-funded by the European Union
Project Coordinator	Dr Angelos Amditis, Institute of Communications and Computer Systems (ICCS), Greece
Consortium	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Institute of Communication and Computer Systems (ICCS), Greece• Fundacion Cidetec (CID), Spain• Ait Austrian Institute of Technology GMBH (AIT), Austria• Fronius International GMBH (FRONIOUS), Austria• Etelatar Innovation OU (ETE), Estonia• Miba Battery Systems GMBH (MIBA), Austria• Dimosia Epicheirisi Ilektrismou Anonymi Etaireia (PPC), Greece• Asociacion Espanola De Normalizacion (UNE), Spain• Sunlight Group Systimata Apothikefsis Energeias Viomichaniki Kai Emporiki Anonymi Etairia (SLG), Greece• Centre Suisse D'electronique Et De Microtechnique Sa - Recherche Et Developpement (CSEM), Switzerland• Ecole Polytechnique Federale De Lausanne (EPFL), Switzerland
Website	battery2life-project.eu
Social Media	Twitter: @battery2life_eu LinkedIn: BATTERY2LIFE Project